

Aug, when disease incidence was recorded, weather favored B1. Average weekly maximum and minimum temperatures were 28.1 and 18.6°C and average relative humidity was 78%. There were 21 rainy days during the month, and intermittent drizzle and cloud cover encouraged disease development. B1 incidence was rated using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice

(SES) 0-9 scale (see table).

At 30 d, 53.79% of the cultivars were resistant; at 40 d only 2.81% were resistant. At 57 d only the resistant check VL8 scored resistant. However, 17 cultivars had some resistance and displayed slow blasting. They were VHC85, VHC218, VHC976, VHC1080, VHC1098, VHC1296, VHC1404, VHC1487,

VHC1488, VHC1493, VHC1494, VHC1508, VHC1583, VHC1759, VHC1760, VHC1761, and VHC1824. These have potential as commercial varieties and for breeding programs to incorporate B1 resistance into improved varieties. □

Negative selection in breeding for quantitative resistance to rice blast (BI) under upland nursery conditions

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In 1983 we evaluated 149 F₄ rice lines for reaction to B1 under upland nursery conditions in Colombia. The entries were derived from crosses between CICA4 (low resistance), IR11-452-1-1 (intermediate resistance), and Tapuripa and Camponi (high resistance). Evaluations were made using the relative evaluation system for B1 and by measuring panicle B1 severity based on disease incidence and intensity.

In the nursery, 70% of the lines with low quantitative B1 resistance in earlier generations had the same reaction in F₅ (see table). However, the reactions of more than 60% of the lines with high or intermediate resistance and the no-infection type differed from those in previous generations.

Field evaluation of a limited number of lines showed that more than 60% of

the intermediate-resistance and no-infection types reacted differently from the previous generations; however, more than 65% of those with high and low resistance gave the same reaction.

A highly susceptible reaction is a reliable indication that a low level of quantitative resistance, compatible races, and a favorable microclimate were all present. But reactions of high and intermediate quantitative resistance, or no-infection type plants alone cannot exclude possible cryptic errors, such as lack of compatible races, insufficient inoculum, or unfavora-

ble microclimate during disease development, particularly in the field.

The results strongly suggest that to attain higher levels of quantitative resistance, which presumably will be more stable, vigorous negative selection made throughout all generations is preferable to positive selection — selection only for plants with less disease. Proper plot design and management are also important to provide a favorable disease environment. Use of diversified inoculum will reduce the masking effect of qualitative resistance on quantitative resistance. □

Change of quantitative resistance to rice blast, Colombia.^a

Resistance in F ₂ , F ₃ , and F ₄	Frequency (%) in F ₅									
	Nursery ^b					Field ^c				
	Total no.	N	N	I	L	Total no.	N	H	I	L
H	28	46	32	18	4	6	17	66	0	17
I	38	10	<u>21</u>	37	32	9	0	<u>22</u>	33	44
L	49	6	8	<u>16</u>	70	19	0	0	<u>5</u>	95
N	34	<u>32</u>	9	26	<u>33</u>	12	<u>33</u>	33	17	<u>17</u>

^a H = high, I = intermediate, L = low, N = no infection. Underlined values indicate % of lines that exhibit the same reaction as in previous generations. ^b Blast nursery at CIAT, Palmira, Colombia. ^c Santa Rosa Station, Villavicencio, Colombia.

Inheritance of moderate resistance to blast (BI) in rice

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We crossed the upland rice cultivars Dourado Precose from Brazil and OS6 from Nigeria, both with moderate resistance to B1 race IH-1 (isolate 43), with susceptible Tongil and highly

resistant Milyang 54. The F₂ plants of the crosses and their parents were screened with the race IH-1. B1 reaction was scored 0 to 9 using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

The reaction of the F₂ seedlings of the crosses Tongil/Dourado Precose and Tongil/OS6 are shown in Figure 1. The score of Dourado Precose was 1-3; that of OS6 was 0 to 4; and that of Tongil was 4 to 9. Both F₂ populations had reaction scores from 0 to 9, with an almost bimodal distribution. Those results indicated that their moderate B1 resistance is monogenic.

If we divide the F₂ segregants into two groups (resistant-moderately resistant and susceptible), based on the infection range of the parents, the segregation pattern is 3:1. However, the peaks of the distribution curves for the resistant and moderately resistant groups did not fit the average of the moderately resistant parents.

When the F₂ populations of the crosses of Dourado Precose or OS6 and Milyang 54 were screened with the same race, the distribution curves were also abnormal (Fig. 2). Milyang 54 scored 0, but the score of Dourado Precose or OS6

1. Frequency distribution of BI scores to race IH-1 in the F_2 of crosses between susceptible Tongil and moderately resistant Dourado Precose and OS6. IRRI, 1984.

2. Frequency distribution of BI score to race IH-1 in the F_2 of the crosses between the highly resistant Milyang 54 and moderately resistant Dourado Precose and OS6. IRRI, 1984.

varied from 0 to 4. Most of the F_2 plants of Milyang 54/Dourado Precose were highly resistant. The reaction scores of most of the F_2 plants of

Milyang 54/OS6 ranged from 2 to 6. However, some highly susceptible segregants were observed for both.

We concluded that the moderate resistance to B1 race IH-1 in Dourado Precose and OS6 is conveyed by major genes with some modifiers. □

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Sheath rot (ShR) in Chhatisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, India

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ShR was first observed in Chhatisgarh in 1978 kharif. Disease incidence has increased, and has significantly reduced yields in some areas. In 1980-82, we field tested several important, commercially grown rice varieties for ShR resistance, based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES) 0-9 scale. Observations were recorded at late tillering to dough stage (see table).

Kranti, Phalguna, Surekha, Pragati, Jaya, Bangoli, and Ratna were infected most severely, particularly in 1981 kharif (20°-30°C temperatures, 65-80% relative humidity). There were many cloudy days during booting. In Phalguna and Kranti, 5-10% of the panicles did not emerge and extensive rotting of the sheaths enclosing the panicles caused significant yield losses. However, Asha, Usha, Safri 17, Dubraj, and Madhuri had some resistance (see table).

The ShR pathogen *Sarocladium oryzae* also causes glume discoloration alone or in combination with other fungi. Highly ShR-susceptible varieties such as Kranti and Phalguna were equally prone to grain discoloration. □

ShR incidence and glume discoloration (GID) in Chhatisgarh, India.

Variety	Disease incidence score ^a during					
	1980		1981		1982	
	ShR	GID	ShR	GID	ShR	GID
Safri	0	0	3	1	3	1
Kranti	7	1	9	7	7	5
Samridhi	3	1	5	3	3	1
Phalguna	5	1	9	7	5	7
Surekha	3	1	7	5	5	3
Pragati	7	3	-	-	5	3
Jaya	3	1	7	5	5	3
Bangoli	-	-	7	3	5	3
Asha	-	-	0	0	3	1
Usha	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ratna	5	1	7	5	5	3
Garima	-	-	-	-	3	1
Madhuri	-	-	3	1	3	1
Dubraj	-	-	0	0	0	1

^aBased on 1980 SES scale.